
INFLUENCE OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT ON STUDENTS’ LEARNING OUTCOME

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ABSTRACT

Formative Assessment is a process which instill a growth mindset among the students. It is such a necessity that students acknowledge the drastic changes that transform their performance after the process of formative assessment. Formative assessment enables a student from diverse section of learners to proceed according to their pace and level of performance. It helps the students’ community to identify their weaknesses, strength, scope, opportunities, threats, faults and the errors till date. Thereafter when they are aware about their own growth and challenges, students are capable to take a smart step and determination towards the next attempt of assessment. Students are able to reflect on their on-going learning style through continuous process of assessment and help them to identify those areas which need improvement. It develops time management and study skills among the students after the formative assessment. It enhances and broadens the understanding regarding learning, examination and required improvement about self. Students can assess about their progress and where they lie during the formative assessment which help them to bounce back when they are informed or make aware on due time. Thus, formative assessment may be in the form of tests, assignments, discussions and queries in the teaching-learning process. In this present study, effort had been taken to highlight the practice of formative assessment in the form of mid-term examinations basically in Cotton University of Guwahati, Assam. The study reveals that formative assessment had a positive impact on their learning outcomes which boosts their performance in the end term examination.

Key Words: Formative Assessment, Influence, Learning Outcome, Progress & Reflect

INTRODUCTION:

In teaching-learning process assessment is a fundamental aspect of the educational experience serving as a critical tool for measuring students learning and achievement. As education evolves to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world, there is an increasing emphasis on the importance of assessment of the learning process itself. Formative assessment is a process that involves strategies used in the classroom for effective learning outcomes. It ranges from test, questions-answers, discussions, mid-terms, observation, performances and many more. Assessment becomes formative when the information is applied to adapt in teaching and learning to meet the students’ needs. It is a process of feedback mechanism for the students as well as for the teachers. When students are given opportunities to know and identify their weaknesses, they can work on it and focus more on the difficulties faced by them. When proper guidance is provided in due time, students can convert their weaknesses into strength. Thus, such activities and initiatives can lead to

improved student success. It can be said that the goal of formative assessment is to monitor and assist students' learning and to provide ongoing feedback for better performance.

In recent years, Educational Research has increasingly focused on the role of formative assessment in fostering an environment where students are encouraged to track their own learning pace. By incorporating strategies such as peer feedback, self-assessment and reflective practices formative assessment facilitates a dialogue between teachers and students, enabling tailored instructional inventions.

Statement of the Problem: The present study is stated as Influence of Formative Assessment on students' learning outcomes.

Objectives of the Study: In this study the objectives are framed as follows-

1. To know about Formative Assessment
2. To find out the influence of Formative Assessment on students' learning outcome

Significance of the Study: Formative assessment enables the teachers and the students to find out the gaps which can also be solved in an instant. A teacher who can apply formative assessment in the classroom genuinely can instill a positive mindset and stir inspiration and motivation in students' mind. It enables a student to identify their own strength and weaknesses and gain an insight towards a better learning performance. A true guide and positive feedback can boost students' aspirations for success and to bring out their best version.

Formative Assessment encourages students to participate actively and instills a mindset of growth and self-awareness in students to emphasize that intelligence and abilities can be developed through firm determination, dedication and hard-work. The present study highlights the significance of formative assessment practices at institutional level with special reference to Cotton University. Cotton University have a special practice regarding formative assessment especially about mid-term examinations. After examinations, before finalizing the result, answer scripts are shown to the students and they can know about their errors and faults if any. Students get to know why they have scored less marks or why few marks have been deducted, so that they become confirmed and clear about the concept and competent about the procedure how to write the answers pertaining the questions. Students benefit a lot from this technique and they could do better in their end term examination. Thus, it proves that formative assessment has a positive impact or influence on students' learning outcomes. It Improves student understanding, it enhances teacher instruction, it boosts students' engagement, it reduces achievement gaps, it fosters a growth mindset, it provides timely feedback and it prepare students for summative assessment. By incorporating formative assessment into their teaching practices, teachers can have a profound impact on students learning outcomes.

Delimitation of the Study: The study is delimited to students of PG 4th semester of Economics and Education Department of Cotton University, Guwahati, Assam.

Operational Definitions of the Key Terms:

Formative Assessment: Formative Assessment includes quick quizzes, mid -term or sessional examinations, discussions, seminars, feedback etc. to monitor students' learning outcomes.

Influence: Influence here refers to the extent to which formative assessment practices affect students' learning outcomes.

Students: Students here refer to 4th Semester Post-Graduate Students.

Learning outcomes: Learning outcomes refers to the academic achievement or students' progress as a result of formative assessment practices.

Methodology of the Study: Methodology provides the context for interpreting the research results and drawing meaningful conclusion. It is the blueprint for a research project and backbone of any research endeavor to produce valid and reliable results. For carrying out the present study, Descriptive survey method has been used. Descriptive survey method was done to know the influence of Formative assessment on students' learning outcomes. This method provides information about what exists at present by determining the nature and degree of the existing condition. It helps in understanding students' opinions, academic and psychological experiences related to formative assessment and its influence on their academic achievement.

Population and Sample of the Study: The Post-Graduate students of 4th semester of Economics Department and Education Department of Cotton University constitute the population of the present. 70 students have been randomly selected as a sample from PG 4th semester of the Economics and Education Department of Cotton University, Panbazar, Guwahati, Assam.

Description of the Study Area: Cotton University is a public state university located in the heart of Guwahati City of Assam, India. It was formally known as Cotton College which was established in 1901. Later it was upgraded to the University in the year 2017 to merge the Cotton College State University and Cotton College. The University provides total of 31 programs under five broad faculties, namely- Physical Chemical and Mathematical Sciences, Life Sciences, Earth Sciences, Language, Literature and Linguistics and Human and Social Sciences. There are around 7000 students from Higher Secondary to PhD Scholars.

Tools Used: In this study, a self- administered questionnaire has been designed to collect necessary information from the students. The questionnaire was constructed on Google form and data were collected through online survey. The questionnaire consisted of 30 close-ended items with response in 'yes or no' format. This format enabled participants to provide clear and concise responses, which were then analyzed and interpreted.

Analysis and Discussion: The raw data collected doesn't reflect any meaning until it has been analyzed and interpreted by a researcher. Thus, analysis and discussion play a vital role in understanding the present data.

Objective 1: To Know about Formative Assessment

Statements	Education		Economics	
	Yes%	No%	Yes%	No%
Aware of present Learning Style	95	5	93	7
F.A. is an essential component of comprehensive evaluation	98	2	100	0
Understanding the purpose of F.A.	100	0	76	23
Able to ask questions and seek help during F.A.	81	19	93	7
Feeling anxious while taking an informal assessment	49	51	73	27
Able to adjust learning strategy based on the	93	7	87	13

feedback				
Recommend the use of continuous assessment in future use	90	10	86	14
Able to reflect on learning through continuous assessment	95	5	90	10

From the above table, it is found that 95% of the student respondents from Education department are aware of their present learning style and only 5% of the students are not aware of their present learning style. On the other hand, it is found that 93% of the students' respondents from Economics Department are aware of their present learning style and only 7% of the students are not aware of their present learning style.

From the above table it shows that 98% of the students from Education think that formative assessment is an essential component of comprehensive assessment. On the other hand, 100% of the students from Economics think that formative assessment is an essential component of comprehensive assessment.

It has been found that 100% of the students from Education understand the purpose of formative assessment. On the other hand, 76% of the students from Economics understand the purpose of formative assessment whereas 23% of the students do not understand.

The table above reveals that 81% of the students from Education responded that they are able to ask questions and seek help during formative assessment and 20% of the students unable to ask and seek help. On the other hand, 93% of the students from Economics responded that they are able to ask questions and seek help during formative assessment and 7% of the students unable to ask and seek help.

It is also found that 49% of the students from Education feel anxious while taking an informal assessment and other 51% of the students do not feel anxious. On the other hand, 73% of the students from Economics feel anxious while taking an informal assessment and other 27% of the students' do not feel anxious.

The table above indicates that 93% of the students from Education are able to adjust their learning strategy based on the feedback received and other 7% of the students unable to adjust. On the other hand, 87% of the students from Economics are able to adjust their learning strategy based on the feedback received and other 13% of the students unable to adjust.

It is also found that 90% of the students from Education recommend the use of continuous assessment in future use while 10% do not recommend. On the other hand, 86% of the students from Economics recommend the use of continuous assessment while 14% do not.

The table also revealed that 95% of the students from Education are able to reflect on their learning through continuous assessment. On the other hand, 90% of the students from Economics are able to reflect on their learning through continuous assessment and 10% of them do not.

Objective 2: To find out the influence of Formative Assessment on Students' Learning Outcomes

Statements	Education		Economics	
	Yes%	No%	Yes%	No%
Progress in learning after mid-term	100	0	93	7

examination				
Formative Assessment methods enhance confidence to prepare for the final evaluation	98	2	93	7
Class tests, assignments serve as progress monitoring tools to support learning	95	5	97	3
Formative Assessment helps identify areas that need improvement	98	2	97	3
Technology based methods make it easier to access feedback and track progress	95	5	93	7
Formative Assessment improves understanding the course material	98	2	97	3
Formative Assessment develops better time management and study skills	93	7	83	7
Formative Assessment reduces stress and anxiety related to exams	76	24	70	30

From the table above, it is found that 100% Of the students' respondents from Education Department can identify their progress in learning after mid-term examination. On the other hand, it is found that 93% Of the students' can identify their progress in learning after mid-term examination.

It is also found that 98% of students from Education and 93% of the students from Economics reveals that formative assessment method enhance confidence to prepare for final evaluation.

The table also reveals that 95% of the students' respondents from Education and 97% from Economics think that class tests, assignments serve as a progress monitoring tools to help them in learning.

The table also reveals that 98% of students from Education and 97% from Economics feel formative assessment help them to identify the areas where they need to improve.

It is found that 95% students from Education and 93% from Economics think that technology-based methods and techniques make it easier for them to access feedback and track their progress.

The table also shows that 98% of the students' respondents from Education and 97% from Economics consider formative assessment have improved their understanding of the course material.

It is found that 93% students from Education and 83% from Economics find that formative assessment is helpful in developing better time management.

The table again reveals that 76% of the students from Education think formative assessment reduces their stress and anxiety related to exams whether 24% of the students do not agree. On the other hand, 70% of the students from Economics think that formative assessment reduces their stress and anxiety while 30% reveals that it do not.

Educational Implications: Formative Assessment is a vital part of the teaching-learning process. In the present study it is been found that students benefit a lot and progress gradually throughout the semester through the process of formative assessment. After the mid-term

examination, students generally gear up and work harder towards identifying their fault and weaknesses and learn the appropriate ways of attempting the questions or writing the answers significantly. Students get enough scope to broaden their understanding and knowledge to pave a better ways and strategies in approaching it. Thus, students and teachers can utilize their strategy for the effective teaching-learning process in their institutions for a fruitful learning process. Formative assessment has the potential to improve learning for transfer and the 21st-century skills.

Formative assessment plays a pivotal role in enhancing students' learning outcomes. Based on the analysis and interpretation, it is suggested that effective formative assessment practices be integrated into instructional strategies to enhance student learning outcomes. Teachers can utilize regular feedback, self-assessment, peer assessment to foster a supportive learning environment. By integrating formative assessments into teaching - learning process educators can create a more effective and student-centered learning experience.

CONCLUSION:

Formative assessment methods are basically the strategies and means that the teachers' uses during interaction in the class and focus on ongoing improvement. In the present study, it is been found that formative assessment is quite applicable to improve the subject's academic achievement. The results of the questionnaire show that the students' attitudes towards formative assessment practices are quite positive. So, teachers and educators need to prioritize the integration of formative assessment into their daily teaching routines. This involves moving beyond traditional testing and embracing a more dynamic and responsive approach to evaluate student learning. Policymakers and administrators should take initiatives to provide teachers with the necessary training and resources to effectively implement formative assessment practices in the daily classroom teaching. Hence it can be concluded that formative assessments have a significant impact on students' learning outcomes by providing ongoing feedback, informing instruction and promoting students' engagement in learning. Formative assessment thus is not merely an educational trend; it is an investment in cultivating critical thinking skills, fostering a love of learning, and ultimately empowering students to reach their full potential.

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